

1 **Genome analysis to understand bacterial adaptation in Benzo[a]pyrene enriched**
2 **environment**

3 Abhisek Dasgupta *

4
5 *Correspondence: Department of Biotechnology, Gauhati University, India. Email: abhisekbiotech@gmail.com

6

7

8 **Abstract**

9 This study investigated the survival mechanisms of bacteria in a hydrocarbon-enriched
10 environment, focusing on factors such as osmotic stress, biofilm formation, and complex
11 carbohydrate utilization. The whole genome of a bacterial isolate (AR19) capable of degrading
12 benzo[a]pyrene (B[a]P) was sequenced and analyzed. The draft genome size was 3.63 Mb, and
13 the closest reference genome was identified as *Bacillus altitudinis*. The genome contained 3777
14 coding genes. Noteworthy findings from the genome analysis included: (i) the involvement of
15 biofilm and biosurfactant in B[a]P adsorption by AR19, (ii) the utilization of extradiol ring
16 cleavage for B[a]P degradation, and (iii) the importance of osmotic stress protection in
17 maintaining cell structure under hydrocarbon stress. The results of this study have potential
18 implications for the development of bioremediation strategies using ex-situ and in-situ
19 techniques.

20 **Keywords:** Hydrocarbon-enriched environment, Benzo[a]pyrene, Biofilm, Biosurfactant,
21 Extradiol ring cleavage, Osmotic stress

22

23

24

25

26 **Introduction**

27 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are group of hydrocarbon compounds having two or
28 more benzene ring fused together. They are exposed to the environment as a result of
29 anthropogenic activities like incomplete burning of fossil fuel or from natural sources (Duran et
30 al., 2016). PAHs possess inherent characteristics, such as their heterocyclic ring structure,
31 hydrophobic nature, and ability to withstand high temperatures, which make them resistant and
32 exceedingly persistent in the environment (Patel et al., 2020). Based on their ring structure they
33 are grouped into low molecular weight and high molecular weight PAHs.

34 16 PAHs were recognized by the US Environmental Protection Agency as significant
35 environmental pollutants (Yuan et al., 2000), out of which Benzo[a]pyrene (B[a]P) is one of
36 them. B[a]P, which belongs to high molecular weight PAHs is also considered to be a potent
37 carcinogen to human, as recognized by International Agency for Research on Cancer
38 (Hardonnière et al., 2016). According to the list prepared by Agency for Toxic Substance and
39 Disease Registry for classification of hazardous environmental pollutants, B[a]P is ranked 8th on
40 the list (Nzila et al., 2021). Therefore, removal of B[a]P from the environment is the need of the
41 hour.

42 In the year 1975, the process of bioremediation was first reported by RL Raymond and
43 coworkers (Litchfield, 2005). Although, this technique has become popular due to its cost
44 effectiveness and sustainability compared to chemical remediation, bioremediation of B[a]P is
45 still in its infancy. Determining the metabolism of B[a]P by *Mycobacterium vanbaalenii* *PYR-1*
46 was an important progress in the field of B[a]P degradation (Moody et al., 2004). In the last
47 decade or so, most of the studies on biodegradation of B[a]P have focused on the metabolic

48 product of B[a]P degradation or on the amount of B[a]P that can be degraded by the microbes
49 (Ostrem et al., 2018).

50 The importance of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria in the process of bioremediation cannot be
51 overstated, as they are responsible for breaking down toxic pollutants into less harmful
52 byproducts. However, their ability to degrade hydrocarbons can be hindered by various stressors
53 in the environment, making it necessary for these bacteria to have a mechanism to tolerate stress.
54 This study's goal is to uncover the underlying molecular and cellular mechanisms that enable a
55 specific bacterium to adapt to hydrocarbon stress and degrade B[a]P, a highly toxic polycyclic
56 aromatic hydrocarbon. By utilizing a combination of cell biology, molecular biology, and
57 bioinformatics techniques, the study aim to provide insights into how the bacterium develops
58 resistance to stress and utilizes B[a]P as an energy source. This knowledge can be useful in
59 developing strategies to enhance the bioremediation of contaminated environments, thereby
60 mitigating the harmful effects of pollutants on both human and environmental health.

61 **Materials and Method**

62 **Genome Assembly.** Screening of B[a]P degrading bacteria was done by spray plate technique
63 (Zhao et al., 2009). The stock solution of B[a]P contained 100µg of B[a]P dissolved in 1 ml
64 dichloromethane. 10µl of the stock solution was used to spray on the plates. Cell viability of the
65 positive isolate in B[a]P containing liquid medium was observed under flow cytometer. The cells
66 were prepared using LIVE/DEAD™ BacLight™ Bacterial Viability and Counting Kit (Thermo
67 Fischer Scientific, Cat no. L34856). Morphology of the cells was observed under Scanning
68 Electron Microscope (Zeiss, Germany). Genomic DNA of the positive isolate was extracted and
69 outsourced for sequencing by Illumina HiSeq platform. Quality check of the raw reads was done
70 by FastQC tool (Andrews, 2010). The adapter sequence was removed by Cutadapt v1.8. Fastp

71 was used to join the trimmed reads (Chen et al., 2018). Kmergenie was used to check the kmers
72 for denovo-assembly (Chikhi et al., 2014). Denevo-assembly was done in SPAdes v3.12.0
73 (Bankevich et al., 2012) using kmer values predicted by Kmergenie. The genome assembly was
74 evaluated using Quast (Gurevich et al., 2013). RAST, Prokka and Glimmer were used to
75 annotate the genome (Aziz et al., 2008; Seemann, 2014).

76 **Bioinformatics analysis.** GTDB –Tk (Genome Taxonomy Database) tool was used for
77 phylogenetic analysis (Arkin et al., 2018). Species tree was constructed using species tree
78 version. A pangenome was computed and plotted against *Bacillus altitudinis* (Taxonomy ID
79 1178544), *Bacillus pumilus* (Taxonomy ID 1408) and *Mycolicibacterium vanbaalenii*
80 (Taxonomy ID 110539). The identification of orthologous group between the genomes was done
81 using OrthoMCL (Li et al., 2003).

82

83 **Results and Discussion**

84 The cell viability of the positive isolate was monitored in a closed system. Therefore, an increase
85 in the microbial biomass raised the percentage of carbon in the medium. Once the dead bacterial
86 cells reached a percentage of above 50, it affected the C:N ratio of the medium. The dead
87 microbial biomass increased the percentage of carbon in the medium and decreased the nitrogen
88 content, which in turn affected the viability. For this reason, the maximum percentage of viable
89 cell was 57.54% (**Figure 1**).

90 The genome assembly was done using k-mer size of 67, 69, 71, 73, 75, and 77. QUAST reported
91 predicted that k-mer of size 73 was the best assembly with largest contig size of 299197 bp and
92 N50 equal to 94,649 bp. The assembly size was 3.63 Mb. The genome (AR19) shared the same
93 branch with *Bacillus pumilus* in a species tree (**Figure 2**), which meant that the genome was

94 closely related to *Bacillus pumilus* and had relatively low genetic divergence with it. The
95 genome also showed closest reference with *Bacillus altitudinis* when the taxonomic
96 classification was done by ANI method.

97 Several protein encoding genes which aid in providing resistance to hydrocarbon stress were
98 annotated in the genome. Particularly, the genes helping in iron uptake, sensing oxygen gradient,
99 biofilm formation, complex carbohydrate utilization, providing UV protection, PAHs
100 metabolism, antiporter and symporter were important in its survival in enriched hydrocarbon
101 environment (**Table 1**). It has been noted that hydrophobic substances causes cell toxicity by
102 inducing water stress (Bhaganna et al., 2010). The positive isolate had large conductance
103 mechanosensitive ion channel (MscL) and OpuA operon in its genome, so it might be possible
104 that the initial response to osmotic stress might be with the help of these genes. MscL channel
105 opens when there is a stretch in the lipid by layer due to water tension. It helps the bacterium to
106 regulate osmotic pressure changes within the cell (Moe et al., 1998). Swelling up of cell of the
107 positive isolate during incubation with B[a]P was also observed in the SEM micrograph (**Figure**
108 **3**). The OpuA operon is expressed under osmotic stress. In *bacillus* species, proline is the
109 principal osmolyte that protects the cell against hypersaline environment (Whatmore et al.,
110 1990). When a *bacillus* sp. is exposed to a hypersaline environment, it takes a very long time for
111 the synthesis of proline to reach a level where it can effectively defend the cell (Boch et al.,
112 1994). So, in order to protect its cell during the initial stage of osmotic stress, the *bacillus* sp
113 synthesizes glycine, betaine from choline which is taken up directly from the environment with
114 the help of OpuA transporter (Kempf et al., 1995).

115 A possible degradation pathway for B[a]P was proposed. Surfactin and biofilm, plays a crucial
116 role in making B[a]P accessible to the positive isolate. Surfactin belongs to the group of

117 biosurfactant that has a good emulsifying property (Pathak et al., 2014). The biofilm helps to
118 stabilize the droplets of B[a]P which has been dispersed in aqueous phase (Omarova et al.,
119 2019). With the help of these two mechanisms i.e. biofilm and biosurfactant production the
120 isolate adsorb B[a]P from the aqueous media. Extradiol ring cleavage mechanism is used by the
121 isolate to degrade B[a]P into carbon source. The putative ring cleaving dioxygenase MhqA starts
122 the cleaving process using molecular O₂. The derivatives are further processed by Catechol-2,3-
123 dioxygenase, encoded by the catE gene, into 2-hydroxymuconate semialdehyde (Xie et al.,
124 2014). It further undergoes catalysis and degraded into pyruvate and acetaldehyde. These are the
125 precursor molecule for energy production in the cell.

126 Pangenome analysis predicted the presence of 13897 homolog families in the protein coding
127 genes of the bacterial genomes (**Figure 4**). The positive isolate had 3555 genes in the homolog
128 family and 222 genes were unique. It was observed that the genes required for degrading PAHs
129 shared a common ancestry within the bacterial genome taken for the pangenome study. Hence,
130 we can infer that hydrocarbon degrading genes are homologous expect for a few special cases.

131 From the genomic data of AR19, it can be hypothesized that the hydrocarbon-degrading isolate
132 possess multiple mechanisms that facilitate its survival in harsh environments. However, it is
133 unclear whether these mechanisms are universal to all bacteria or specific to hydrocarbon-
134 degrading bacteria. Therefore, future research should aim to elucidate the unique characteristics
135 of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria, taking into account all the cellular mechanisms that might be
136 responsible for providing protection against hydrocarbon stress.

137

138 **Data Availability**

139 The draft genome of AR19 can be accessed from the NCBI data with accession number
140 **QAWE00000000**

141 **Acknowledgement**

142 I am thankful to both of my supervisor Prof P.J. Handique (Vice Chancellor, Gauhati University)
143 and Dr. Ratul Saikia (CSIR-NEIST) for providing facilities for conducting the research.

144

145 **Funding**

146 Funding for genome sequencing was provided by Dr. Ratul Saikia (CSIR, NEIST).

147

148 **Conflict of Interest**

149 There is no conflict of interest.

150

151 **Reference**

- 152 1. Andrews, S. (2010). FastQC: A Quality Control Tool for High Throughput Sequence
153 Data [Online]. Available at: <http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>
- 154 2. Arkin, A. P., Cottingham, R. W., Henry, C. S., Harris, N. L., Stevens, R. L., Maslov, S.,
155 ... & Dehal, P. (2018). KBase: The United States Department of Energy Systems Biology
156 Knowledgebase. Nature Biotechnology, 36, 566. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.4163>.
- 157 3. Aziz, R. K., Bartels, D., Best, A. A., DeJongh, M., Disz, T., Edwards, R. A., ... &
158 Zagnitko, O. (2008). The RAST Server: Rapid Annotations using Subsystems
159 Technology. BMC Genomics, 9, 75. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2164-9-75>.
- 160 4. Bankevich, A., Nurk, S., Antipov, D., Gurevich, A. A., Dvorkin, M., Kulikov, A. S.,
161 Lesin, V. M., Nikolenko, S. I., Pham, S., Prjibelski, A. D., Pyshkin, A. V., Sirotkin, A.

- 162 V., Vyahhi, N., Tesler, G., Alekseyev, M. A., & Pevzner, P. A. (2012). SPAdes: A new
163 genome assembly algorithm and its applications to single-cell sequencing. *Journal of*
164 *Computational Biology*, 19(5), 455-477. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cmb.2012.0021>.
- 165 5. Bhaganna, P., Volkers, R. J., Bell, A. N., Kluge, K., Timson, D. J., McGrath, J. W.,
166 Ruijsenaars, H. J., & Hallsworth, J. E. (2010). Hydrophobic substances induce water
167 stress in microbial cells. *Microbial Biotechnology*, 3(6), 701-716.
168 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-7915.2010.00203.x>.
- 169 6. Boch, J., Kempf, B., & Bremer, E. (1994). Osmoregulation in *Bacillus subtilis*: Synthesis
170 of the osmoprotectant glycine betaine from exogenously provided choline. *Journal of*
171 *Bacteriology*, 176(17), 5364-5371. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jb.176.17.5364-5371.1994>
- 172 7. Chen, S., Zhou, Y., Chen, Y., & Gu, J. (2018). fastp: An ultra-fast all-in-one FASTQ
173 preprocessor. *Bioinformatics*, 34(17), i884-i890.
174 <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty560>.
- 175 8. Duran, R., & F, C. (2016). Role of environmental factors and microorganisms in
176 determining the fate of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in the marine environment.
177 *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*, 40(6), 814-830. doi: 10.1093/femsre/fuw031.
- 178 9. Gurevich, A., Saveliev, V., Vyahhi, N., & Tesler, G. (2013). QUASt: quality assessment
179 tool for genome assemblies. *Bioinformatics*, 29(8), 1072-1075.
180 <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btt086>.
- 181 10. Hardonnière, K., Saunier, E., Lemarié, A., et al. (2016). The environmental carcinogen
182 benzo[a]pyrene induces a Warburg-like metabolic reprogramming dependent on NHE1
183 and associated with cell survival. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 30776. doi: 10.1038/srep30776.

- 184 11. Kempf, B., & Bremer, E. (1995). OpuA, an osmotically regulated binding protein-
185 dependent transport system for the osmoprotectant glycine betaine in *Bacillus subtilis*.
186 *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 270(28), 16701-16713.
187 <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.270.28.16701>.
- 188 12. Li, L., Stoeckert, C. J. Jr., & Roos, D. S. (2003). OrthoMCL: Identification of ortholog
189 groups for eukaryotic genomes. *Genome Research*, 13(9), 2178-2189.
190 <https://doi.org/10.1101/gr.1224503>.
- 191 13. Litchfield, C. (2005). Thirty years and counting: Bioremediation in its prime?
192 *BioScience*, 55(3), 273-279. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-
193 3568\(2005\)055\[0273:TYACBI\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2005)055[0273:TYACBI]2.0.CO;2)
- 194 14. Moe, P. C., Blount, P., & Kung, C. (1998). Functional and structural conservation in the
195 mechanosensitive channel MscL implicates elements crucial for mechanosensation.
196 *Molecular Microbiology*, 28(3), 583-592. [https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-
197 2958.1998.00821.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2958.1998.00821.x).
- 198 15. Moody, J. D., Freeman, J. P., Fu, P. P., & Cerniglia, C. E. (2004). Degradation of
199 benzo[a]pyrene by *Mycobacterium vanbaalenii* PYR-1. *Applied and Environmental*
200 *Microbiology*, 70(1), 340-345. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.70.1.340-345.2004>.
- 201 16. Nzila, A., Musa, M. M., Sankara, S., Al-Momani, M., Xiang, L., & Li, Q. X. (2021).
202 Degradation of benzo[a]pyrene by halophilic bacterial strain *Staphylococcus haemoliticus*
203 strain 10SBZ1A. *PLoS One*, 16(2), e0247723.
204 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0247723>.
- 205 17. Omarova, M., Swientoniewski, L. T., Tsengam, I. K. M., Blake, D. A., John, V.,
206 McCormick, A., Bothun, G. D., Raghavan, S. R., & Bose, A. (2019). Biofilm Formation

- 207 by Hydrocarbon-Degrading Marine Bacteria and Its Effects on Oil Dispersion. ACS
208 Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering, 7(17), 14490-14499.
209 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.9b01923>.
- 210 18. Ostrem Loss, E. M., & Yu, J. -H. (2018). Bioremediation and microbial metabolism of
211 benzo(a)pyrene. Molecular Microbiology, 109, 433-444.
212 <https://doi.org/10.1111/mmi.14062>.
- 213 19. Patel, A. B., Shaikh, S., Jain, K. R., Desai, C., & Madamwar, D. (2020). Polycyclic
214 Aromatic Hydrocarbons: Sources, Toxicity, and Remediation Approaches. Frontiers in
215 Microbiology, 11, 562813. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2020.562813.
- 216 20. Pathak, K. V., & Keharia, H. (2014). Application of extracellular lipopeptide
217 biosurfactant produced by endophytic *Bacillus subtilis* K1 isolated from aerial roots of
218 banyan (*Ficus benghalensis*) in microbially enhanced oil recovery (MEOR). 3 Biotech,
219 4(1), 41-48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-013-0119-3>.
- 220 21. Seemann, T. (2014). Prokka: rapid prokaryotic genome annotation. Bioinformatics,
221 30(14), 2068-2069. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu153>.
- 222 22. Whatmore, A. M., Chudek, J. A., & Reed, R. H. (1990). The effects of osmotic upshock
223 on the intracellular solute pools of *Bacillus subtilis*. Journal of General Microbiology,
224 136(12), 2527-2535. <https://doi.org/10.1099/00221287-136-12-2527>.
- 225 23. Xie, Y., Yu, F., Wang, Q., Gu, X., & Chen, W. (2014). Cloning of catechol 2,3-
226 dioxygenase gene and construction of a stable genetically engineered strain for degrading
227 crude oil. Indian Journal of Microbiology, 54(1), 59-64. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s12088-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12088-013-0411-2)
228 [013-0411-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12088-013-0411-2).

229 24. Yuan, S. Y., Wei, S. H., & Chang, B. V. (2000). Biodegradation of polycyclic aromatic
230 hydrocarbons by a mixed culture. *Chemosphere*, 41(9), 1463-1468. doi: 10.1016/s0045-
231 6535(99)00522-6.

232 25. Zhao, B., Wang, H., Mao, X., & Li, R. (2009). A rapid screening method for bacteria
233 degrading polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. *Letters in Applied Microbiology*, 49(3),
234 408-410. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-765X.2009.02668.x>.

235 26. Rayan Chikhi , Paul Medvedev, Informed and automated k-mer size selection for genome
236 assembly, *Bioinformatics*, Volume 30, Issue 1, January 2014, Pages 31–37,
237 <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btt310>.

238

239

240

241

Figure

Figure1. Dotplot generated from the flowcytometer data of AR19. It was observed that the maximum percentage of viable cell of AR19 was 57.54% observed after 7 days of incubation.

Figure2. Species tree of AR19. AR19 shared the same branch with *Bacillus pumilus*. It means both these bacteria shared a common ancestry.

Figure3. SEM micrograph showed that the cells of AR19 swelled up after incubation in B[a]P. From this it can be inferred that the cells of the bacterial isolate went through osmotic stress when subjected to hydrocarbon environment,

Figure4. A pangenome circle plot with 1 resembling *Bacillus altitudinis*, 2 *Bacillus pumilus*, 3 *Mycobacterium vanbaalenii* PYR-1. The core genome that is AR19 was assigned 0 in the plot. Red color indicated the singleton genes.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Bacillus altitudinis
■ base singletons
■ non-core
■ core

Pangenome
■ non-core
■ core

Figure 4

Table1. Annotated proteins of AR19 bacterial isolate and their proposed function

Protein	Function
Protease Htpx	Stress
Subtilisin E	Biofilm
HemAT	Stress
YcIN	Siderophore
4-4 diaphytoene desaturase	Stress
Aerobactin synthase	Siderophore
Methionine Synthase	Survival
Multidrug resistance protein	Efflux of toxic intermediate or bioproduct produced in hydrocarbon degradation
Sulphate permease CysP	Uptake of sulphate
Motility protein SwrD	Helps in coordinate movement of bacterial cells. Can help in biofilm formation
UvrABC system	Nucleotide excision repair (UV protein)
Purine Efflux pump PbE	Export of purine out of the cell
Thioredoxin 1	Redox signaling homeostasis chaperone oxidative stress
Membrane bound negative regulator	Biosynthesis of exopolysaccharide
Catechol 2-3 dioxygenase	Ring cleavage of catechol catabolism of aromatic compound
Succinate-acetate proton symporter	Metabolism of organic acid . pH balance
Copper transport protein	Involved in the uptake of Cu(II) ions and is

	found in copper resistant bacteria
Divalent metal cation transporter	Helps bacteria to acquire manganese from the environment
Protein FixA	Chaperone
Citrate Transport	Energy metabolism
Thermostable monoacylglycerol	Glycerol conversion, It acts as cryoprotectant
Adapter protein	Resistance to antibiotics
Sulfate/thiosulfate import ATP-binding protein CysA	Utilization of sulfur-containing compound as nitrogen
ABC-type transporter ATP-binding protein EcsA	Helps bacteria to use ethanolamine as nutrient source in various environment
Amino-acid permease RocC	Protection against low pH (acidic) condition
Serine protease Do-like HtrB	chaperone
Beta-xylosidase	Hemicelluloses breakdown
Isoprimeverose transporter	Carbon source
Anaerobic nitric oxide reductase transcription regulator NorR	Adaptation to anaerobic environment
Corrinoid adenosyltransferase	Biosynthesis of vitamin B12
Xylose isomerase	Carbon source
Dimethyl sulfoxide reductase DmsA	Biogeochemical cycling of sulphur
H₂HPP isomerase	Degradation of aromatic compound
Carboxylesterase	Degradation of aromatic compound
Mercuric resistance operon regulatory	Resistance to mercury

protein	
GABA permease	pH stress
Altronate oxidoreductase	Pectin degradation
Cold shock protein CspC	Helps in regulation of gene expression in response to cold shock
Monocarboxylic acid transporter	Anaerobic respiration
Nitronate monooxygenase	Helps to metabolize Nitroalkanes
Alkanesulfonate monooxygenase	Protects against oxidative stress
Large-conductance mechanosensitive channel	Regulation of osmotic stress
Putative ring-cleaving dioxygenase MhqO	Putative ring-cleavage dioxygenase that may contribute to the degradation of aromatic compounds

From the table it is clear that the positive isolate has evolved several mechanisms in its genome to survive environment promoting hydrocarbon stress. Therefore, in order to develop a bioremediation strategy we should take into account all the possible mechanism given above in combination with the degradation efficiency of the bacteria.